

Fatigue of out-of-plane fibre waviness defects: experimental and numerical study

Supratik Mukhopadhyay¹, Stephen R. Hallett²

^{1,2}Advanced Composites Centre for innovation and science, University of Bristol
Queens Building, University Walk, Bristol, BS8 1TR

Email: s.mukhopadhyay@bristol.ac.uk, stephen.hallett@bristol.ac.uk

Web page: www.bristol.ac.uk/composites

Keywords: Defects, Fatigue, Delamination, Finite elements

ABSTRACT

Manufacturing defects are major limiting factors in the application of composite structures in aerospace sector because in-service damage can initiate from these defects and lead to premature failure. Out-of-plane fibre waviness or 'wrinkling' is a defect which is known to reduce the pristine tensile strength considerably under quasi-static loading. It therefore, is crucial to investigate the performance of laminates with embedded wrinkles under fatigue loading because the prematurely initiated damage sites can grow in a stable manner under relatively low load and subsequently can cause failure.

In this study, quasi-isotropic ($[+45/90/-45/0]_{3s}$) carbon fibre/epoxy laminates containing artificially induced out-of-plane fibre waviness defects of controllable severity were manufactured by inserting additional uncured pre-preg material in such a way as to introduce no new interfaces or foreign objects into the laminate. These were tested in tension-tension fatigue with various loading severities (percentage of the quasi-static failure load). Failure was considered when the degraded stiffness of the specimens was reduced to a critical percentage of the initial undamaged stiffness. The damage development was observed by taking images of the gauge section at regular intervals during test. Some tests were interrupted part way through the damage development and inspected using X-ray computed tomography to visualise the damage state inside the laminates. All tests were run up to 10^6 cycles unless failure happened earlier. In all the cases a significant amount of delamination was observed in the region of the waviness defect. A three dimensional finite element model of the wavy specimen was developed following the actual geometry of the wavy plies in the test specimens. Delamination failure was simulated using a novel user defined cohesive material formulation. A Paris-based fatigue degradation law was embedded into the material formulation. This modelling technique was shown to be an effective tool to predict delamination failure arising from defects in composites in fatigue loading.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the last few decades, the use of composite to make structural parts has become common in the aerospace and automobile sectors. This has necessitated new design philosophies including a thorough understanding of failure mechanisms of composites under varied loading conditions. Delamination between plies is a major failure mode in composites which initiates at relatively low loads and reduces the overall structural properties significantly[1]. For rotating components made from composites investigation of delamination due to fatigue loading is crucial, since these components are subjected to a large number of loading cycles in a relatively short period of time.

Delamination can often initiate from pre-existing manufacturing defects such as voids, wrinkles or embedded foreign objects. Wrinkle or out-of-plane fibre waviness is a manufacturing defect and is commonly found in thick-section composite structures. Wrinkles are characterised by the formation of localised band of wavy fibres through-the-thickness of the laminate. Some possible reasons for wrinkle formation are: laying up on a highly curved tooling whereby constrained excess material near the radii promotes wrinkle formation, or automated fibre placement heads turning on small radii during laying-up, thus resulting in fibres buckling out-of-plane, or non-uniform pressure distribution during cure causing formation of resin rich areas and fibre waviness etc. The severity of wrinkles are quantified by

three parameters: the waviness length λ , amplitude δ and waviness angle θ (see Figure 1). Upon load application, inter-laminar shear stresses localise at the wrinkle causing early failure. Although such detrimental effect of wrinkles under quasi-static loading conditions are well documented in literature, investigation of failure due to these defects under fatigue loading is relatively scarce. Recently, Nikishkov et al [2] studied fatigue delamination initiation and growth in multidirectional laminates containing wrinkle defect under tension-tension load conditions. Stress-based initiation criteria were combined with available S-N curve test data to predict number of cycles to failure under mixed-mode loading. A simple linear stiffness degradation scheme to simulate damage in the structure was implemented as a user material in a finite element framework. The model predictions were compared with tests and was shown to capture the location of damage initiation and the number of cycles to failure satisfactorily.

Figure 1: Waviness parameters used to quantify wrinkle severity

In this work, delamination behaviour in quasi-isotropic laminates containing an embedded wrinkle was investigated in tension-tension fatigue loading with an R ratio of 0.1 at various loading severities (percentage of quasi-static failure load). An existing technique [3] was used to artificially introduce wrinkles of controllable severities in the laminate. The initiation and growth of delamination was monitored from camera images taken at regular interval of elapsed cycles. Finite element models were built in LS-Dyna following the geometry of the actual test specimens. Cohesive interface elements inserted between solid ply elements were used to model delamination. A fatigue degradation law equipped with a novel crack-tip tracking algorithm [4] was embedded in the cohesive material formulation which was used to simulate the damage in the numerical model, as seen in tests.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

2.1 Wrinkle specimen manufacture details

Quasi-isotropic $[+45/90/-45/0]_{3s}$ laminates were made using Hexcel's IM7/8552 carbon-epoxy material system with a nominal ply thickness of 0.25mm. This lay-up was used in previous studies [3] by the authors and is representative of lay-ups used in industrial practice. The specimen dimensions were 250mm×30mm×6mm with 150 mm gauge length. A wrinkle of controllable severity was intentionally induced in the central region along the gauge length by laying up thin strips of 90° plies on full length 90° plies, thus promoting wrinkle formation (see Figure 2(a)). This method did not need any pre-cured or foreign substance to be introduced in the laminate to create the artificial wrinkle defect, which might have otherwise inadvertently led to formation of weaker interfaces and overshadowed the effect of the wrinkle alone towards delamination failure. Two different grades of wrinkle severity were manufactured by varying the thickness and position of 90° strips in the lay-up. They were designated as L#1 and L#2 respectively, with higher number indicating higher wrinkle angle. Approximately eight to ten specimens were made for each wrinkle severity. The wrinkle angles were measured by taking microscope images of the polished gauge section of the laminate and recording the angle which a tangent aligned with the wavy ply made with a straight reference ply (see Figure 2(b)). The measured average wrinkle angles for L#1 and L#2 specimens were 5.5 ° and 8.2° respectively.

Figure 2: (a) Artificially inducing waviness using the strip-insertion method. (b) Measurement of wrinkle angle by tangent drawing technique.

2.2 Fatigue testing

One specimen for each of the two wrinkle severities was quasi-statically failed in tension and the corresponding failure load levels were recorded to confirm that this batch matched previous results [3]. Fatigue tests were done in a 100 kN Instron machine at various severities of the static failure load with an R-ratio (minimum load/maximum load) of 0.1. For the L#1 wrinkle specimens, 40, 50, 60 and 70 percent loading severities were chosen for study while for the L#2 specimens, tests were restricted to only 40, 50 and 60 percent loading severities. This was because, when loaded quasi-statically, nearer 70 percent of the final failure load, the L#2 specimens consistently showed a small load-drop accompanied by delamination at the wrinkle [3]. This delamination propagated upon further monotonic loading, resulting in fibre fracture as the final point of failure. Therefore, in the fatigue study, 70 percent loading severity was avoided for L#2 specimens in order to not have any ambiguity in the definition of failure load (which was taken to be the final maximum failure load level) and to avoid any damage happening at the very first loading cycle. Failure in fatigue was defined as a certain percentage loss in initial undamaged modulus of the wrinkle specimens. All specimens were tested to 10^6 cycles unless failure happened earlier. A baseline frequency of 3Hz was used for 60 percent loading severity and adjusted linearly for other loading severities to keep the loading rate constant. To more closely observe delamination growth in the laminate during test progress, a camera was focused on the gauge section (see Figure 3), which captured images at regular cycle intervals by halting the machine for 500 ms at peak load. This was achieved by controlling the machine operation from an external LabVIEW programme. In addition, a thermal camera was employed which served two purposes; firstly ensuring the temperature rise due to cyclic loading was not critically high to adversely affect the resin properties, and also the localised temperature rise was used as a means of observing damage growth inside the structure. Further to this, some tests were interrupted during damage growth and the specimens were scanned using X-ray computed tomography (CT) to see the internal state of delamination.

Figure 3: Experimental set-up for tension-tension fatigue testing

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

3.1 Cohesive element framework for fatigue delamination with crack-tip tracking

Delamination in fatigue between plies was modelled using an existing formulation due to Harper and Hallett [5] implemented as a cohesive user-material in reduced integration hexahedral solid elements in LS-Dyna. This approach employed a cycle-jump strategy to model high cycle fatigue behaviour in composites. Using this strategy, the numerical load in the model was smoothly ramped up from zero to the peak load, and held constant. A finite number of cycles were assumed to have elapsed in a given model run time denoted as ‘pseudo time’ (see Figure 4(b)). The cohesive material formulation for fatigue delamination is briefly discussed here for completeness.

Figure 4: (a) Relative displacement components in a cohesive element (b) Cycle-jump strategy for numerical modelling.

The relative nodal displacements between the top and bottom surface of the cohesive element were projected on the mid-plane (see Figure 4(a)) and transformed to a local coordinate system. The relative normal displacement was denoted by δ_{33} and the two shear displacements were denoted by δ_{13} and δ_{23} respectively. An effective mixed mode displacement δ was defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_I &= \langle \delta_{33} \rangle & (1) \\ \delta_{II} &= \sqrt{\delta_{13}^2 + \delta_{23}^2} \\ \delta &= \sqrt{\delta_I^2 + \delta_{II}^2} \end{aligned}$$

where Macaulay bracket on δ_I indicates that negative normal displacement does not participate in the damage constitutive law, for it would cause crack closure. Before damage initiation, stiff spring connections K_I and K_{II} between the top and bottom surfaces of the cohesive element were assumed which related mode I traction σ_I with mode I displacement δ_I and mode II traction σ_{II} with mode II displacement δ_{II} . A stress-based quadratic interaction criterion was used for initiation of delamination damage:

$$\sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_I}{\sigma_{I \max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{II}}{\sigma_{II \max}}\right)^2} = 1 \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_{I \max}$ and $\sigma_{II \max}$ are the mode I and mode II strengths respectively. Once Eq. (2) was satisfied, the propagation of delamination was governed by two laws. The first one is the baseline bilinear law for quasi-static damage, where the damage was purely a function of displacement across the cohesive interface. Failure was defined by a power law criterion:

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}}\right)^\alpha = 1 \quad (3)$$

where G_I and G_{II} were the mode I and mode II energy release rates. The power law exponent α was taken as unity for simplicity. The subscript 'c' indicated the fracture toughness in the respective modes. A mixed-mode damage parameter D_s [0,1] was established for quasi-static damage:

$$D_s = \frac{(\delta - \delta_e)}{(\delta_f - \delta_e)} \quad (4)$$

where the subscript 'e' and 'f' on δ indicated mixed mode displacement corresponding to damage initiation and complete failure respectively. This damage variable was used to linearly reduce the cohesive traction components from their value at initiation to zero at complete failure. The second law, which was the fatigue degradation law, was activated once an element was quasi-statically damaged and a user given fatigue initiation time (with respect to the model run time or 'pseudo-time') was met. Under cyclic loading, a Paris law was used to govern fatigue delamination propagation:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C \left(\frac{\Delta G}{G_c}\right)^m \quad (5)$$

where a is the length of delamination, N is the number of elapsed load cycles, ΔG denotes the strain energy release rate amplitude, and G_c is the mixed-mode critical energy release rate. C and m are mixed-mode Paris law parameters derived from experimentally obtained mode I parameters C_I , m_I and mode II parameters C_{II} , m_{II} using a suitable interpolation scheme. ΔG was derived from the peak value of the energy release rate G_{\max} :

$$\Delta G = G_{\max} (1 - R^2) \quad (6)$$

where R is the ratio between the minimum load and maximum load which was taken as 0.1 in the present study. A fatigue damage parameter D_f was introduced following Robinson et al [6]. Once da/dN (crack growth per unit cycle) was determined, based on a user given cyclic loading frequency dN/dt , the damage growth per unit cycle dD_f/dN could be found which could be used to update the fatigue damage parameter. The total damage parameter D_{tot} , due to combined quasi-static and fatigue damage was defined as:

$$D_{tot} = D_s + D_f \quad (7)$$

which was used to degrade the cohesive traction components to zero at complete failure. However, as detailed in [5], the derivation of dD_f/dN from da/dN required the knowledge of the cohesive zone length under mixed-mode conditions which was not easy to obtain. To get around this problem, Kawashita & Hallett [4] proposed a method of tracking the crack-tip as damage progresses. Instead of applying the fatigue formulation on the entire cohesive zone (and thereby requiring the knowledge of the length of the cohesive zone), fatigue was selectively applied on elements pertaining to the crack tip. In that case, an effective element length l_e could be derived in a straightforward manner. Then, the number of cycles

ΔN_e within which an element on the crack-tip failed was given by:

$$\Delta N_e = \frac{dN}{da} l_e \quad (8)$$

Once an element was quasi-statically damaged by an amount D_s , to fail it completely, an additional damage of $1-D_s$ was needed to be done by fatigue. Therefore, the fatigue damage growth per unit cycle dD_f/dN was given by:

$$\frac{dD_f}{dN} = \frac{1-D_s}{\Delta N_e} \quad (9)$$

With the help of the user given cyclic loading frequency dN/dt , the updated fatigue damage parameter at pseudo-time t was incrementally obtained:

$${}^t D_f = {}^{t-\Delta t} D_f + \frac{dD_f}{dN} \frac{dN}{dt} \Delta t \quad (10)$$

where Δt was the stable time increment size of the explicit dynamic analysis. Following Eq (10), Eq. (7) was updated for the total damage, and the cohesive tractions were degraded with the simulation progress.

3.2 Finite element mesh of wrinkle specimen

A representative finite element mesh of the L#2 wrinkle specimen was developed (see Figure 5) which contained 178290 solid hexahedral elements. The wavelength and amplitude of the wrinkle was measured from microscope images and was input into a MATLAB script which generated the waviness profile through-the thickness using a sinusoidal approximation [3]. For computational efficiency, only 90mm of the gauge length was modelled. Cohesive elements of thickness 0.01mm (with the fatigue degradation formulation described in Section 3.1) were inserted between ply elements of thickness 0.25 mm. A finer mesh of in plane aspect ratio 0.5mm×0.5mm was used in the wrinkle, while a coarser mesh 1.5mm×1.5mm was used away from the wrinkle.

Figure 5: Finite element mesh of the L#2 wrinkle specimen showing the central region of waviness.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Experiment

The stiffness E of the specimens were determined from the applied maximum and minimum load P_{max} and P_{min} (obtained from the LabVIEW programme), the nominal cross-sectional area A_0 and extensometer (attached to the specimen) reading for maximum and minimum tensile strain ϵ_{max} and ϵ_{min} as given:

$$E = \frac{P_{\max} - P_{\min}}{A_0(\varepsilon_{\max} - \varepsilon_{\min})} \quad (10)$$

For all the specimens tested, a normalised stiffness E/E_0 was established, where E_0 indicated the initial undamaged stiffness and E indicated the current stiffness, degraded due to fatigue. A critical value of the normalized stiffness was taken as the point of failure.

The cross-sectional stress level for L#1 wrinkle configuration corresponding to complete failure in quasi-static tension was 710.5 MPa. As described in previous work [3], the corresponding failure mode was fibre tensile failure due to axial plies getting overloaded as a result of delamination between ply interfaces. When loaded in tension-tension fatigue at 50%, 60% and 70% of the quasi-static failure load level, damage was consistently found to happen due to delaminations appearing from the +45/90 and 90/-45 interfaces closer to the laminate surface rather than the embedded wrinkle in the middle. Figure 6 shows camera images of a specimen loaded at 50% severity highlighting delamination initiation and growth. The 40% loading severity gave a runout (no noticeable failure) at 10^6 cycles (Figure 7(a)). Failure was defined in this case to be a loss of 20% of the initial undamaged stiffness E_0 and an S-N curve was established. Tests were also interrupted near the failure point and X-ray CT scanning was done. The CT scan data was post processed to reveal the damage state. In Figure 7(b), a specimen loaded at 50% severity is shown which was interrupted just before failure. Major delaminations coming from the edge (rather than the wrinkle) could be identified which indicated a less critical effect of the wrinkle defect on failure in this case. Dispersed matrix cracks in 90 and +/- 45 plies could also be observed.

Figure 6: Damage sequence in a L#1 specimen loaded at 50% loading severity. Stiffness (normalised) vs elapsed cycles (left) and camera images corresponding to the marked points (right). The centralized wrinkle profile is highlighted using a blue line and cracks/delaminations highlighted using red arrows.

Figure 7: (a) Loading severity vs number of cycles (S-N) curve for L#1 specimens. (b) Interrupted test at 50% loading severity showing major delaminations along the laminate edges. Matrix cracking in +/- 45 and 90 plies can also be seen.

For the L#2 specimens, the cross-sectional stress level corresponding to complete quasi-static tension failure was 649.2 MPa. Similar to L#1, the final failure mode was fibre tensile failure, interacting with preceding delaminations. In fatigue, it was noticed that the delamination behavior was different from the L#1 specimens such that, major delamination originated and propagated from the 90/-45 and +45/90 interfaces in the wrinkle rather than from the laminate edges. This was attributed to the higher wrinkle severity of the L#2 specimens. A clear change of slope was observed in the normalized modulus vs. number of cycles curve (see Figure 8) associated with delamination at the wrinkle. This was consistently observed among all the loading severities tested (40%-60%). Camera images of the damage sequence of a specimen loaded at 50% loading severity is shown in Figure 8 and the delamination growth in the wrinkle is highlighted. Because the failure mechanism for this level of wrinkle severity was different compared to the L#1 wrinkle, the failure definition was changed to a loss of 8% of initial undamaged stiffness E_0 which encompassed the observed change of slope for all the loading severity cases tested. A corresponding S-N curve is shown in Figure 9(a). A specimen loaded at 50% severity interrupted near the failure point is shown. Major delaminations through the width localised at the wrinkle could be observed clearly.

Figure 8: Damage sequence in a L#2 specimen loaded at 50% loading severity. Stiffness (normalised) vs elapsed cycles (left) and camera images corresponding to the marked points (right). The centralized wrinkle profile is highlighted using a blue line and cracks/delaminations highlighted using red arrows.

Figure 9: (a) Loading severity vs number of cycles (S-N) curve for L#2 specimens. (b) Interrupted test at 50% loading severity showing delaminations localized in the wrinkle . Matrix cracking in +/-45 and 90 plies are also seen.

4.2 Model

The parameters used as model input are given in Table 1 and Table 2. A preliminary study was done to assess the effectiveness of the delamination fatigue routine implemented in LS-Dyna. A 60% loading severity was considered for the L#2 specimen (dominated by delamination at the wrinkle as mentioned in Section 4.1). Before applying any mechanical load to the model, the residual stress development in the specimen due to cooling down from cure temperature to room temperature through a temperature difference of 160°C was modelled by assigning a thermal load curve. Afterwards, the mechanical loading was applied and linearly ramped up from zero to the maximum peak load (see Figure 4(b)) and held constant. The fatigue was activated after a small time-dwell to ensure all dynamic effects in the model were stabilised. A numerical frequency of 1000 Hz was used in the model. Results for progressive fatigue delamination growth with the crack-tip track routine in a 90/-45 interface are shown in Figure 10. The values of $\sigma_{I_{max}}$ and $\sigma_{II_{max}}$ that were required to be used to generate this result are lower than the actual material strengths. This is because the fatigue model formulation is based on propagation due to a Paris type curve and without sufficient stress concentration to initiate static damage, fatigue damage does not accumulate. For this model, failure was recorded at ~ 400 cycles which slightly prematurely predicts the mean experimental failure (Figure 9(a)). Development of the full numerical S-N curve with improved formulations is part of on-going and future work.

Figure 10: (a)-(c) Fatigue delamination progress in a 90/-45 interface of the laminate (top view). (d) through -thickness profile of delamination localized in the wrinkle defect.

E_{11} (MPa)	E_{22} (MPa)	E_{33} (MPa)	γ_{12}	γ_{13}	γ_{23}	G_{12} (MPa)	G_{13} (MPa)	G_{23} (MPa)	α_{11} (/°C)	α_{22} (/°C)	α_{33} (/°C)
161000	11380	11380	0.32	0.32	0.43	5170	5170	3980	0	3e-5	3e-5

Table 1: Undamaged thermos-elastic properties of IM7/8552 [3]

K_I (N/mm ³)	K_{II} (N/mm ³)	$\sigma_{I\max}$ (MPa)	$\sigma_{II\max}$ (MPa)	C_I	C_{II}	m_I	m_{II}	G_{Ic} (N/mm)	G_{IIc} (N/mm)	α
10^5	10^5	30	60	6.51E-3	6.69E-2	5.290	6.376	0.26	1.002	1

Table 2: Material properties for quasi-static/fatigue damage of cohesive elements [4], [5]

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, delamination fatigue behaviour of quasi-isotropic laminates containing embedded wrinkle defects located centrally along the gauge-length is analysed. Two different grades of wrinkle severities are manufactured and tested in tension-tension fatigue. The lower grade of wrinkle severity was seen not to critically affect the failure behaviour and delaminations initiated from the edge of the laminate. On the contrary, for the higher severity wrinkle, failure was predominantly due to the delaminations originating and growing from the wrinkle defect. A novel numerical algorithm was implemented and applied to simulate delamination failure in a finite element model of the wrinkle specimen. This modelling technique is presently under development and shows promise to be used as a tool in future to predict delamination initiation and growth in composite structures containing defects.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge Rolls-Royce plc for the support of this research through the Composites University Technology Centre (UTC) of the University of Bristol. Also, Dr. O.J. Nixon-Pearson is acknowledged for post-processing of the CT scan data of wrinkle specimens.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Martin, "Delamination fatigue," in *Fatigue in Composites*, B. Harris, Ed. Woodhead Publishing Ltd., 2007, pp. 173–188.
- [2] Y. Nikishkov, A. Makeev, and G. Seon, "Progressive fatigue damage simulation method for composites," *Int. J. Fatigue*, vol. 48, pp. 266–279, 2013.
- [3] S. Mukhopadhyay, M. I. Jones, and S. R. Hallett, "Tensile failure of laminates containing an embedded wrinkle; numerical and experimental study," *Submitted*, 2015.
- [4] L. F. Kawashita and S. R. Hallett, "A crack tip tracking algorithm for cohesive interface element analysis of fatigue delamination propagation in composite materials," *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, vol. 49, no. 21, pp. 2898–2913, 2012.
- [5] P. W. Harper and S. R. Hallett, "A fatigue degradation law for cohesive interface elements - Development and application to composite materials," *Int. J. Fatigue*, vol. 32, no. 11, pp. 1774–1787, 2010.
- [6] P. Robinson, U. Galvanetto, D. Tumino, G. Bellucci, and D. Violeau, "Numerical simulation of fatigue-driven delamination using interface elements," *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 63, no. April, pp. 1824–1848, 2005.